

Unsupervised learning for detection of mobility related anomalies in commercial LTE networks

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Abstract—We propose an unsupervised learning based anomaly detection framework for identifying cells experiencing performance degradation due to mobility problems, in LTE networks. Handover failure rate is used as a performance metric, whereas the mobility problems considered include too-early and too-late handovers. In order to enable unsupervised learning, the framework leverages existing datasets in commercial LTE networks (e.g. performance management counters, configuration management data, geographical locations, and inventory data etc). To this end, the first step is data pre-processing, followed by feature extraction based on principal component analysis and clustering. For implementation, we use real data from an operational commercial LTE network. Results show that clustering is highly effective in understanding and identifying mobility related anomalous behaviour, and provides actionable insights for automation and self-optimization, paving the way for efficient mobility robustness optimization, which is an important self-optimization use-case for contemporary 4G/5G networks.

Index Terms—Unsupervised learning, anomaly detection, clustering, mobility robustness optimization, 4G, 5G

I. INTRODUCTION

Mobile networking technologies are evolving rapidly, in response to the growing demand for high data rates, better coverage, and low latency. As a consequence, networks are becoming not only increasingly dense, but also highly dynamic and heterogeneous, leading to new challenges for operators in terms of performance and the quality of service provided to end users. In this context, emerging 5th generation (5G) networks entail substantial differences compared to contemporary 4th generation (4G). In particular, 5G focuses on new directions, such as massive machine-type communications, enhanced mobile broadband, and ultra-reliable and low-latency communications for providing a wide variety of services. 5G is designed to support new types of frequency bands, multi-connectivity, wide range of mobility and radio access technologies. To fulfill these requirements in

an effective and cost-efficient manner, intelligent automation and self-organization is of paramount importance.

The concept of self-organizing networks (SON) emerged as a complementary solution to automate configuration and network management tasks in 4G mobile networks. In fact, SON often comprises of a set of functions that allow the network to self-plan, self-configure, self-optimize, and self-heal, with minimal human intervention and correct/prevent network failures. SON use-cases have proven their effectiveness in reducing capital and operational expenditures by not only minimizing the need for human intervention, but also improving network performance and user experience via a better utilization of network resources. Therefore, there is a lot of interest from mobile operators, vendors, and standardization and governing bodies, in exploring the potential of SON for 5G and beyond networks. For instance, European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI) launched a zero-touch group to investigate automation. An important step towards this direction is the enhancement of current SON use-cases using artificial intelligence based approaches. This has been facilitated by the advent of big data platforms, processing capabilities that enable implementation of both supervised and unsupervised machine learning techniques [1].

This paper proposes unsupervised learning approach for detecting mobility related anomalies, pertinent to mobility robustness optimization (MRO) — an important SON use-case for contemporary 4G networks and 5G. Relevant existing approaches include [2], where authors propose reinforcement learning to reduce the call drop rates. In [3], [4], the authors discuss fuzzy logic capabilities. Likewise, a number of papers address the problem by identifying successful handover events through unsupervised learning [5], [6]. In particular, these works propose an approach to handover management based on self-organizing map analysis. The idea is to exploit the experience gained from the analysis of data of the network based on user equipment (UE) measurements, to learn where handovers have occurred and decide whether to allow them or not. Finally, the work in [7] considers real network data to reduce mobility problems without causing significant increase in the number of handovers. However, the proposed approach does not apply any learning algorithm for analysis. Our ap-

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Fig. 1: Unsupervised learning framework

proach makes use of principal component analysis (PCA) and clustering to detect patterns of handover failures from a large number of cells in a commercial LTE network. It involves the following steps: 1) detection of anomalous behavior in cells and identification of cells with similar behaviors, 2) selection of the most representative features, and 3) actions to mitigate the problems.

The outline of the paper is as follows. The overall approach is described in Section II. It shows the main steps including data pre-processing and unsupervised learning algorithms such as PCA and clustering. Section III presents the details regarding implementation, which uses datasets from a commercial LTE mobile network. Section IV discusses results and provides a comparison of different approaches. It also recommends actions to mitigate mobility problems. We conclude in Section V.

II. UNSUPERVISED LEARNING FRAMEWORK FOR MOBILITY RELATED ANOMALIES

A. Preliminaries

The main objective of MRO is to guarantee proper mobility or handover performance by mitigating common handover problems such as too-early and/or too-late handovers. Cell pairs with such problems leave a peculiar anomalous data pattern/signature different from those with normal handovers. Once failure patterns have been discovered, we aim at grouping cell pairs with similarities. Clustering is used to find correlations between mobility problems and cell pair characteristics. The new insights are then used to re-cluster with the aim of obtaining more specific groups. The whole process is depicted in Fig. 1 and described in the rest of the section.

B. Data Pre-processing

The first step is to clean the data and identify quality features to discover important characteristics, and make the first hypotheses about the hidden information. A key challenge is that mobile network datasets are very diverse in terms of volume, granularity, and update frequency, ranging from almost static inventory management (IM) data, to semi-static parameter configuration management (CM) data, to highly dynamic performance management (PM) counter data. Furthermore, generic problems arise due to the fact that data formats are very diverse and vary between vendors, and even among pieces of equipment from the same vendor. Other quality issues often exist and need to be tackled, for

example, lost, incomplete, or inconsistent data due to sporadic malfunction of devices.

C. Anomaly Detection

Consider a cell $i \in \mathcal{I}$ with a set of neighboring cells \mathcal{J}_i . Let $p_{i,j} \in \mathcal{P}_i$ denote an ordered cell pair comprising cell i as source and its neighbour j as destination in the handover process. \mathcal{P}_i is the set of all pairs having cell i as the source cell. The number of cell pairs in the whole network is $N_p = |\mathcal{P}|$, where $\mathcal{P} = \bigcup_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \mathcal{P}_i$. The performance of a cell pair is derived by taking into account too early and late handovers at cell pair level. Let $N_E^{i,j}$ and $N_L^{i,j}$ denote the number of early and late handovers, aggregated over M days, between cell i and neighboring cell j , respectively.

We use total handover failure rate (HOFR) $R_{HOFR}^{i,j}$ as a cell pair level performance metric, given by $R_{HOFR}^{i,j} = N_A^{i,j} / N_T^{i,j}$, where $N_A^{i,j} = N_E^{i,j} + N_L^{i,j}$ is the number of abnormal handovers and $N_T^{i,j}$ is the total number of handovers between cell i and neighboring cell j , and $N_E^{i,j}$ and $N_L^{i,j}$ denote the number of early and late handovers (between cell i and neighboring cell j), respectively. Note that $R_{HOFR}^{i,j}$ may be dependent on a host of factors such as geographical location, speed, distance, parameter configuration etc. Also, these factors manifest themselves as extractable features in the data. Let us assume that mobility performance for a given cell pair $p_{i,j}$ is impacted by $d \in \mathbb{Z}^+$ features. Let $\mathbf{x}_i = [x_{i,1} \dots x_{i,d}] \in \mathbb{R}^d$ denote the vector of data features for cell pair $p_{i,j}$. The data for all the cell pairs is collected in a matrix

$$\mathbf{X} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{x}_1 \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{x}_{N_p} \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_p \times d},$$

which is the input to PCA, as explained next.

1) *PCA*: The purpose of employing PCA is feature extraction, i.e. to discover features contributing to mobility problems. It reduces the total number of features, while capturing all salient information of the original features in such a way that it is possible to reconstruct the original dataset from the reduced dataset. The anomaly score for cell pair \mathbf{x}_i is then the sum of the squared differences between the original feature matrix and the reconstructed matrix. That is, the reconstruction error is used as the anomaly score, thus the algorithm assigns each cell pair an anomaly score between zero and one. Cell pairs that have the largest sum of squared differences will have an error close to one.

We keep only the first L parameters, the resulting transformation can be expressed as $\mathbf{T}_L = \mathbf{X}\mathbf{W}_L$, where $\mathbf{T}_L \in \mathbb{R}^{N_p \times L}$ consists of principal component scores of the first L components, and $\mathbf{W}_L \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times L}$ is a matrix of weights whose columns are eigenvectors of $\mathbf{X}^T \mathbf{X}$ [8]. The transformed data \mathbf{T}_L serves as an input to clustering algorithm.

2) *Clustering*: Clustering algorithms aim at identifying patterns, forming clusters of cell pairs with similar characteristics, according to some kind of criteria. We focus on the hierarchical clustering algorithm called Hierarchical Density Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise

(HDBSCAN), which combines a hierarchical approach with the basic DBSCAN algorithm. In the DBSCAN algorithm, clustering is done based on the density of data points. It is different from other cluster algorithms in the sense that we do not need to specify the number of clusters and we not need to cluster outliers. However, the maximum distance between data points for them to be considered in the same neighborhood ϵ is needed to be specified, along with the minimum number of samples S_{\min} for a group to be called a cluster. However, in HDBSCAN, we obtain a complete dendrogram where each ϵ -cut corresponds to an epsilon clustering of the DBSCAN. In each ϵ -cut, the HDBSCAN allows us to associate each cell pair to a specific cluster or to be considered as noise [9].

We use HDBSCAN for partitioning \mathbf{T}_L , the resulting partition $\mathcal{C} := \text{HDBSCAN}(\mathbf{T}_L, S_{\min}, \epsilon\text{-cut})$ comprises of K labelled clusters $\mathcal{C} := (C_1, \dots, C_k, \dots, C_K)$. In order to analyze uniqueness characteristics of resulting clusters, we follow the *variance within variables and between clusters* approach. Accordingly, if the average value of a given variable ordered by the clustering algorithm differs significantly among resulting clusters, that particular variable is likely to have an important role in creating the clusters. Once the most important features have been identified using this methodology, the clustering algorithm is run again with the identified features, rather than the original set of principal components.

D. PM Data

Mobility related performance counters collect the mobility related data of cellular network at regular intervals with a very high granularity (e.g. 15 minutes to one hour). For a given time interval, the mobility problems are stored as the aggregate of too-late, too-early and ping pong handovers generated in each cell pair during a given time interval. While the resulting time series are typically on the same scale, the number of observations in a given time interval can vary. To deal with this irregularity, the original data is used to compute new PM data features given in top half of TABLE I.

E. CM/IM Data

For source cell and target cell in a given cell pair, data available from inventory and configuration management sources includes cell ID, latitude, longitude, name of the site and eNB, region ID, type of antenna, value of bearing(s) and frequency bands, among others. The bottom half of TABLE I includes the additional features computed with this data.

F. Movement and Speed Data

Besides the new features generated and the cell-level data coming from the operation and support system of a live LTE network, UE locations and velocity measurements are also considered. The data is generated from actual traces downloaded from the Google Maps API. This API allows us to get information such as speed limits and way points of different travel modes (i.e. driving, walking, bicycling and public transportation). By using this information and the cell size of each cell pair, we estimate the moving speed of UEs likely to be present in the coverage area.

PM Data Features		Description
Number of observations of each cell pair during a given time interval		Number of hours that each cell pair fulfills initial selection criteria during the time interval set to one month
Pair time of observation		Number of observations per hour in one month
Ratios of early, late and ping-pong observations		Number of hours in which the mobility problem rate is above 10%, 25% and 50% divided by the number of observations
Ratio of handover successful observations		Number of hours in which the successful rate is above 10%, 25% and 50% divided by the number of observations. The rate is calculated as the ratio between successful handovers divided by the total number of handovers
CM/IM Data Features		Description
Pair distance		Distance between source and target cells
Cell size		Based on the latitude, longitude, and bearing, we compute the expected cell size of each cell as the 90 percentile distance to the neighboring cells
Type of cell pairs		Based on the antenna type, enhanced Node B (eNB) and sector of the source and target cells
Inter-Intra bands	frequency	For each cell pair, it indicates if the source cell have same frequency band that the target cell (Intra-frequency bands) or not (Inter-frequency bands)

TABLE I: Features extracted from PM, CM, and IM data

Before applying PCA, $\mathbf{y} = [y_1 \dots y_i \dots y_{N_p}]$ is generated by labeling $y_i = 1$, for cell pairs with HOFR greater than 10%, and zero otherwise. Once the dataset is pre-processed and normalized, it is split into training and testing parts. Training set ($\mathbf{X}_{\text{train}}, \mathbf{y}_{\text{train}}$) comprises 2/3 of the data, whereas the rest is used as test set ($\mathbf{X}_{\text{test}}, \mathbf{y}_{\text{test}}$). In our experiments, $\mathbf{X}_{\text{train}}$ consisting of 119202 cell pairs with similar characteristics.

III. IMPLEMENTATION USING COMMERCIAL LTE NETWORK DATASETS

For implementation of the proposed approach, we use LTE network datasets from a major Finnish mobile operator. The total number of cell pairs in the dataset is $N_p = 177914$. Data sources used and associated features are diverse as explained in the following discussion.

IV. RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

In order to analyze the performance of the PCA algorithm, we compare it to different linear dimensionality reduction algorithms, such as independent component analysis (ICA) and kernel principal component analysis (KPCA). ICA differs from PCA in that the axes are not orthogonal. As a result correlation between the axes is not zero. We also compare results with the KPCA, which is a nonlinear version of PCA.

For performance analysis, we consider the precision recall and the receiver operator characteristic (ROC) curves. From figures 2 and 3, we observe that by using $L = 10$ principal components, we are able to predict 82% of the handover failures with an average precision of 81%. This means that we detect 17518 cell pairs, which represent 81% of the total 21628 cell pairs with HOFR above 10% in the training set. From these figures, it can be observed that ICA gives similar

Fig. 2: Precision-recall comparison of dimensionality reduction algorithms

Fig. 3: ROC comparison of dimensionality reduction algorithms

results. Finally, KPCA is able to detect only 73% of the cell pairs with HOFR above 10% with 81% precision. Recall that the input to the clustering algorithm is a data matrix of size 119202×10 , $S_{\min} = 300$ and $\epsilon\text{-cut} = 0.75$. To estimate the overall accuracy from HDBSCAN, we consider the sum of the counts of the most frequently occurring observations across all the clusters divided by the total number of observations. Clustering using HDBSCAN with the training set leads to $K = 6$ clusters with an overall accuracy of 0.82. Moreover, it labels 86013 cell pairs as outliers.

As explained in Section II, the variance within variables and between clusters is calculated to understand what makes each group unique. Based on the generated clusters, we retrieve the mean value per variable, calculate the variance of means between clusters within each variable and select the top 15 variables with the highest variance. Fig. 4 shows the variables with the highest variance. It shows the most important variables and how much they differ among each cluster. We notice: 1) clusters C_0 to C_3 covers most of

Fig. 4: Results of the first clustering (features with highest variance, namely (a) inter-intra frequency bands, (b) HO rate = late 25%, (c) HO rate = late 50%, (d) HO rate = late 10%, (e) HO success ratio = 50% and (f) HO success ratio = 25%). The description of each feature is given in TABLE I

Fig. 5: HOFR heatmap after re-clustering. Overall accuracy of HDBSCAN is 0.85, and the size of the noise group is 62935

the too-late handovers. The variables with highest variance corresponds to the ratio of too-late handovers higher than 10%, 25%, and 50%, while clusters C_4 and C_5 represent the healthy groups, i.e., these contain cell pairs with high probability of successful handovers.

Fig. 6: Statistics of Cluster C_0 (HOFR > 90%)

It is important to note that at this point, we already know the most important features in creating the clusters. Therefore, we re-cluster, but instead of using L principal components for each cell pair, we use the features depicted in Fig. 4. As a consequence, the algorithm creates $K = 43$ clusters instead of $K = 6$ created previously. Thus, by using relevant features, the algorithm is able to detect in detail the problematic cell pairs. In Fig. 5, the HOFR heatmap after re-clustering is shown. The x-axis represents the frequency band while the y-axis represents the cluster IDs. From this figure, we notice that clusters C_0 , C_5 , and C_6 contains cell pairs with HOFR greater than 90%.

In order to evaluate the consistency of each group of family with respect to different variables and find a correlation with different characteristics, we quantify the prevalence of different types of cell pairs and features within these groups. For instance, Fig. 6 shows the normalised histograms of cluster C_0 . It shows the proportion of mobility problems that fall into each of several features. That is, each histogram shows the correlation among the mobility problems considering the type of cell pairs that most frequently appears in each group and different features of those cell pairs. The type of cell pairs that most frequently appears in this cluster is the one where the source cell has more than one bearing (categorized as MIMOsc), and both source and target cells belong to different sites. Furthermore, we observe that for all those cell pairs the handover failures are caused by late handovers, i.e., those cell pairs do not have problems of early nor ping pong handovers. The rest of the clusters with high HOFR (see Fig. 5) share the same characteristics. The difference between cluster C_5 and C_6 is in the type of cell pairs, while the difference between cluster C_{15} and C_{16} is in the type of frequency bands. Therefore, each cluster is unique.

Based on analysis of results, it is possible to devise strategies for each cluster, e.g., those cell pairs belonging to clusters with handover failures caused by too-late handovers can be isolated and fixed later by adjusting their handovers parameters in an automated manner. For instance, a MRO algorithm based on such approach would select only those pairs where: (1) at least one of the cells has more than one bearing, and they do not share sector, (2) involve inter frequency bands, (3) number of observations less than 100, meaning cells with very scarce UE transfer, (4) too-early and ping pong rates are equal to 0, and (5) the maximum speed of UEs which are likely to be present is greater than 50 Km/h. The next step would be to increase the cell individual offset parameter of the source cell with respect to the target cell. The algorithm can be evaluated based on the HOFR in each source cell. As a result, the number of abnormal handovers in those cell pairs will be reduced.

V. CONCLUSIONS

We have proposed a unsupervised learning framework, which makes use of dimensionality reduction algorithms such as PCA, in conjunction with hierarchical clustering algorithm HDBSCAN, to identify cells with anomalous behaviour in terms of handover performance. For feature extraction, apart from geographical information and UE velocities, real LTE network data consisting of diverse data sources is used, which facilitates extraction of relevant features leading to highly accurate predictions. Results suggest that the presented approach leads to efficient identification of anomalous patterns in handover performance data, leading to improved insights. Therefore, this approach can be used to develop better data driven MRO algorithms.

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